

Study on Aflatoxin Toxins in Vietnam

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Abstract:

The paper conducts analytical analysis of the theoretical basis of aflatoxin toxins from the origin, aflatoxin-producing species, reproductive species, chemical activity and mechanisms of toxic effects. aflatoxin element. Based on that theory, we conduct a situation analysis in Vietnam with special conditions on environment and climate. We analyzed this toxin on a number of species such as Chicken Duck and mechanism of action on humans. Finally, we offer solutions to control and prevent this toxin.

Keywords: aflatoxin toxins, Vietnam

1. Introduction

In the world today, the study of the level of mold and mycotoxin contamination on food and food is an important issue to protect human and animal health. The aflatoxin toxin is mainly produced by the fungi *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus parasiticus*, which are the most dangerous and often contaminated on agricultural products, causing toxicity to humans and cattle, such as causing acute effects, causing liver damage (liver cancer ...), teratogenic, mutagenic, ... even in high doses can lead to death. Of the many aflatoxins in nature, aflatoxin B1 is considered to be the most dangerous toxin. Although the presence of *Aspergillus flavus* is not always associated with the presence of aflatoxin in its toxic content, it also presents a significant risk of possible aflatoxin contamination.

In Vietnam, with the hot and humid tropical climate, the humidity in the air is often high, the cultivation and harvest seasons often fall in the rainy season while the means of harvesting, drying agricultural products are poor, storage It is not guaranteed to be dry and cool, which is a very favorable condition for mold growth to cause toxins for food and animal feed.

In 1960, poultry farming in England was severely damaged, initially over 10,000 turkeys died of a new disease called "Turkey X disease" (Turkey X disease). Later, other poultry such as ducks and pheasants also became infected and died a lot. Through investigation, it was determined that the disease is related to a toxin caused by fungi in food. By 1961 it was discovered that the chemical nature of this toxin was Aflatoxin caused by the fungi *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus parasiticus*. Aflatoxin has 4 important derivatives namely AFB1, AFB2, AFG1, AFG2. Among the above 4 types, Aflatoxin B1 accounts for the most in agricultural products and causes the most damage, causing the fastest and most common poisoning.

In 1961, studies recognized that Aflatoxin was produced by the fungus *Aspergillus flavus* and could be the cause of tumors in the animal's liver. In aquatic animals, the first studies of Aflatoxin toxin on salmon were conducted by Ashley et al.

Since then, there have been many studies on Aflatoxin toxin. Scientists have also identified the molecular formula and structural formula of Aflatoxin.

Aflatoxin residue control is therefore essential and important. Limits of aflatoxin contamination have been one of the standards of food safety.

2. Literature review

2.1. Species capable of producing Aflatoxin

Aflatoxin is usually produced by two familiar fungi, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus parasiticus*, with different amounts depending on the type of fungus, substrate, climatic conditions and the environment.

Some other molds also produce Aflatoxin in very small quantities: *Penicillium puberulum* Bai, *Aspergillus* strains such as *Aspergillus tamarii*kita, *Aspergillus niger* tiegh, *Aspergillus ostiamis* wehmen, *Aspergillus ruper*.

However, there is a lot of controversy because *Aspergillus flavus* develops during development, it is often mixed with many other fungi, especially with *Penicillium rubrum* stoll and then Aflatoxin may be mistakenly produced by *Penicillium*.

In some cases, it may be confused with the toxins Sterigmatocystin and Avecsin because of the chemical structure close to Aflatoxin.

Aspergillus flavus

Aspergillus parasiticus

2.2. Aflatoxin production conditions

The ability to produce toxins of *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus parasiticus* is very different. It depends on factors such as mold strains, substrates, temperature factors, substrate moisture and environment.

Vaccine toxin

- Aflatoxin is produced from two strains of *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus parasiticus*.
- Not all of the *Aspergillus flavus* strains surveyed produced Aflatoxin, only 73% were capable of producing Aflatoxin, of which 23% produced Aflatoxin at the highest level. Many important changes have been recorded according to the substrate from which *A.flavus* strains have been isolated and according to geographical origin. For example, of the 284 rice isolates in the United States, 94% of the strains had the toxin, 86% for the peanut isolates were also in the country and only 71% for the samples. isolated also from compassion but in Israel.
- In addition, the amount of Aflatoxin also varies greatly depending on the strain.
- In addition to quantifying the total number of Aflatoxins, it is also important to determine the partial proportions of different known Aflatoxins. In general, Aflatoxin B1 is most produced in nature and culture, then Aflatoxin G1, then very far Aflatoxin B2, and Aflatoxin G2 and other Aflatoxins are quite low.
- Distinguishing toxin and non-toxin strains through morphological characteristics: mycotoxins with green spore tip attached, even in long-term cultured varieties (double-layer flasks, stem cells attached to the wall with thorns).
- A toxin strain can lose that ability through repeated inoculation on synthetic media. But the virulence of a strain is increased by successive inoculation in appropriate natural media.

Mechanical and environmental

- Substances are oily seeds, especially peanuts and groundnut products. The highest amount of toxins contained in peanuts. Strains isolated from rancid meat, bread, raw food or contaminated cheese naturally have no or very little ability to produce toxins. In contrast, nearly one-third of the strains isolated from spices were capable of producing Aflatoxin.
- Even on the same substrate, the ability of *Aspergillus flavus* to produce Aflatoxin varies. The cause of this phenomenon may also be because some peanut varieties are resistant to *Aspergillus flavus* producing toxin Aflatoxin. Breeders have relied on the discovery to create peanuts free from aflatoxin contamination. This is the research that many scientists use to eliminate Aflatoxin in the most beneficial way.
- The formation of Aflatoxin depends on the mycelium biomass and development time, the more mycelium volume, the more toxin produced and vice versa. The time to maximize Aflatoxin production is usually from the sixth to the seventh day afterwards. The reason for the reduction of Aflatoxin levels in the following days is due to the mold itself.
- The most suitable temperature for Aflatoxin production of molds is from 25-28°C. If *Aspergillus flavus* is cultured at 45 ° C, the ability to produce Aflatoxin will be inhibited.
- The content of water in the substrate plays an important role in the formation of Aflatoxin. In peanuts, the amount of water is 15-30%, the formation of Aflatoxin appears after 2 days; rice needs 24-26% of water and 19-24% for corn. Thus, it can be said that the production of Aflatoxin occurs very quickly. Especially after harvesting, substrate has high water content, prolonged drying time is the cause of Aflatoxin contamination.
- Initial pH of the environment has little effect on Aflatoxin formation; No matter how much it is, there is always a tendency towards a value between 4 and 5.
- Carbon source: the effects of adding hexose sugar to the culture media on *A.flavus* yield were investigated and concluded that glucose, fructose and manose were favorable for Aflatoxin synthesis.

Table 1: Gluxit

Gluxit	Concentration	
	1%	3%
D glucose	+++	+++
D manose	+++	+++
D fructose	+++	+++
D galactose	-	++
D gulose	-	0
D arabinose	-	-
D xilose	+	++
D ribose	-	+
D eritrose	-	0
D glyxerandehyt	+++	+++

- Nitrogen source: on the environment with nitrite protein, *A.flavus* secretes little Aflatoxin; on ammonia, uric acid and glutamic acid, *A.flavus* produces more; So in the classic Czapeck formula, NaNO_3 is replaced by NH_4Cl or another ammonium salt. The highest amount of Aflatoxin is found on yeast or peptone media or, better yet, amino acids. Tiamin and B-group vitamins that stimulate the synthesis of Aflatoxins, riboflavin and piridoxins have no effect.

- Metal ions: the presence of Zn, Mg or Fe stimulates the ability to produce Aflatoxin; Co, Cr, Mn, Ca have little effect.

- Other substances: When *A.flavus* develops on wheat grains, the amount of Aflatoxin produced in the embryonic stage is much higher than in the embryonic stage. In addition, it was found that adding lipid (extracted from wheat germ with pentane) to a substrate consisting of wheat germ removed lipid has a good effect on Aflatoxin production. The beneficial effect of fatty acids on the well-known toxin formation makes people think that they play an important role in the biosynthesis of Aflatoxins; Their biodegradation results in the formation of precursors involved in the Aflatoxin biosynthesis cycle. Adding dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) to the culture medium will cause the Aflatoxin concentration to either increase slightly or decrease significantly. This is probably more of a reciprocal metabolic effect than a chemical reaction between DMSO and Aflatoxins.

2.3. Chemical structure

Aflatoxins are commonly contaminated on plant products. Approximately 18 different types of aflatoxin have been found, but the four most common ones, including the four compounds of the bis-furanocoumarin group, are metabolic products made by *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus parasiticus*. named as B1, B2, G1, G2.

Four substances are distinguished on the basis of their luminescent colors. B stands for Blue (blue) and G is Green (green). Thin-layer chromatograms, obtained from chloroform: methanol-extracted water (98.5: 1.5) were separated by a chloroform system: carbon tetrachloride: water: methanol (2: 2.5: 1: 3) detected two traces of sulfur. photosynthesis under ultraviolet light: one is a bluish-violet fluorescence, which is aflatoxin B1, another with a lower R_f and a green fluorescence, which is aflatoxin G1. Aflatoxin G1 is very close to the aflatoxin B1 structure: it has two lactone functions, and aflatoxin B1 has only one. By deactivating the terminal hydrofuran nucleus of dihydroaflatoxin B1 and G1, two other toxic products, aflatoxin B2 and G2, were obtained. Compared with aflatoxin B1, their toxicity to ducklings is 60 to 100 times worse; so they are not toxic, otherwise the possibility of losing the carbohydrates converted to aflatoxin B1 is very toxic.

Aflatoxin B1 and B2 in cow's milk are metabolized and called Aflatoxin M₁ and Aflatoxin M₂ (M is an abbreviation of Milk). Aflatoxin M₁ has violet blue fluorescence, aflatoxin M₂ has lower R_f and violet fluorescence. Aflatoxin M₁ is hydrogen - 4 aflatoxin B1, and aflatoxin M₂ is hydrogen - 4 aflatoxin B2.

Of the four types of Aflatoxin, Aflatoxin B1 is usually found at the highest concentration, followed by G1, while B2 and G2 exist at lower concentrations.

AFLATOXIN B₁

AFLATOXIN B₂

AFLATOXIN M₁

AFLATOXIN M₂

AFLATOXIN G₁

AFLATOXIN G₂

In addition to the six main types of aflatoxin, several other types of aflatoxins were discovered. It was suggested to call those compounds as flavatoxin or flavacuramin:

- Aflatoxin P1: is a metabolic product, is a phenolic derivative of aflatoxin B₁. They have been isolated on column ambeclit XAD - 2 (Rohm and Haas). Its molecular weight, determined by mass spectrometry, is 2.8. This product is a result of methyl reduction of aflatoxin B₁.

- Aflatoxin 3B or toxin B3: a low R_f substance, isolated from *A. flavus* culture flasks, crystalline, yellowish, aflatoxin B₁ from 40 to 50 times less toxic.

- Aflatoxin B3 (isolated by Siubblefield and colleagues) is also called porositicol: the final xiclopentene of aflatoxin B₁ is replaced by an ethanol side chain, so this substance is 6 - metoxi -7 - (2 '- hidroxietyl) difurocumarin.

3. Mechanism of action of Aflatoxin

Aflatoxin B₁ is a strong affinity molecule with intestinal wall, low molecular weight so it is easily absorbed completely after eating.

Upon arrival in the small intestine, Aflatoxin B₁ will quickly be absorbed into the vein and small intestine, duodenum.

From the gastrointestinal tract, according to the portal vein, Aflatoxin is most concentrated in the liver (accounting for about 17% of the body's Aflatoxin), followed by the kidneys, muscles, adipose tissue, pancreas, spleen and 80% is excreted. for about a week and it is worth noting that it is also excreted via the mammary gland causing the fetus to breastfeed. The plasma half-life is 36.5 minutes, the distribution is 14% of the body weight, the release from the body is 1.25 L / kg / h.

Aflatoxin M₁ is mainly excreted within 48 hours (Hendrickse 1991).

So far, scientific conclusions have recognized the ability of Aflatoxin to affect liver cells through 5 stages:

- Inhibit polymerase enzymes which synthesize DNA and RNA.
 - Slow down or stop DNA synthesis completely.
 - Prevent the mechanism of RNA biosynthesis for transmission
 - Changing the shape of cell nucleus.
 - Limiting protein biosynthesis.
- Consequently causes carcinoma of liver cells.

Due to the chemical structure with a dihydro-furan ring, Aflatoxin B1 binds with some enzymes that hinder metabolism leading to death.

In the liver, Aflatoxin B1 (AFB1) is metabolized by the cytochrome p450 enzyme group (in humans P450 III A4 for adults and P450 III A6 for the fetus) to form many metabolic products such as Aflatoxicol, Aflatoxin Q1, Aflatoxin P1, and Aflatoxin M1, depending on the genetic predisposition of the species. For humans, most Aflatoxin B1 is converted into AFQ1, in addition to AFM1, aflatoxicol (AFL), AFLH1, AFP1, AFB2a and AFB1-2, 2-dihydrodiol.

The Cytochrome P450 IIIA4 enzyme activates and detoxifies AFB1, and, through metabolic processes, the resulting products include toxic metabolites (epoxides) from epoxidation and less toxic metabolites from hydroxy and demethylation. Only 8, 9-exo epoxide cause mutations and others are detoxification products.

Under the catalysis of the enzyme glutathione-S-transferase, the conjugation of epoxides and glutathione (GSH, an endogenous tripeptide synthesized from cells by three amines: cysteine, glutamic and glycine, binds to toxins in the liver, metabolizing them and excreting them) is formed, reducing the DNA alteration caused by epoxides. Humans have less glutathione-S-transferase to 8.9-epoxide activity than mice, so they are less likely to detoxify this important metabolite.

AFB1 epoxides can react with nuclear nitrogen, other atoms with oxygen and sulfur components in the cell (Guengerich et al. 1996). This active substance can combine with specific DNA components, guanine, to induce alterations in the DNA (Hendrickse 1991). This is possibly the most important carcinogenic product.

The exo isomers of aflatoxin B1 (AFB 1) 8,9-epoxides cause mutations by interfering with the middle of the DNA by forming a guanine-conjugated product by reaction with guanine 7N atoms. Although epoxides hydrolyze rapidly in H₂O (0.6 s⁻¹ at 25 ° C), the DNA conjugated products are still very high.

In the human body, AFB1 is mainly converted into aflatoxin B1-N7 guanine conjugated product. Interpolation of epoxides causes G to T conversion in codon 249 of the p53 gene in the liver (AGG → AGT: Arg → Ser), which can lead to liver damage and liver cancer.

In addition, during circulation, Aflatoxin B1 is attached to plasma proteins, especially albumin, to form aflatoxinalbumin (Autrup et al. 1991). AFB1 8,9-exo epoxides after hydrolysis form AFB1-dihydrodiol, which continuously oxidizes dialdehyde and condenses with S-amino group of lysine. This additive product is a completely changed protein-aflatoxin structure that retains only the coumarin and cyclopen-tenone rings of the original compound. The average half-life of albumin in humans is about 20 days. Therefore, aflatoxin accumulates in the long term when albumin is present.

For other organs in the body, Aflatoxin influences the electron transport chains that interfere with the cytochrome system - reducing ATP, inhibiting ATPase, and causing mitochondrial swelling, preventing cell energy production.

In addition, an increase in AFB1 - 8, 9 epoxides significantly increased the amount of lipid peroxide. (Toskulkao et al. 1982). Peroxidation of membrane lipids deprives cell membrane integrity, limits enzyme activity and membrane lysis (Younes and Siegers 1984; Toskulkao et al. 1982; Toskulkao and Glinsukon 1988). AFM1 and AFG1 form glucoronide or sulphate conjugates that are excreted in the urine. Collagen products with DNA and AFB1-N7-guanine are also excreted in the urine, Aflatoxin M1 and M2 are excreted in milk. The conjugated AFB1-glutathione is excreted primarily via bile.

Aflatoxin B1 is nearly equivalent to aflatoxin M1. Aflatoxin M2 is less toxic than aflatoxin M1. The aflatoxin B2 and G2 are much less toxic than aflatoxin B1. It was also found that without the dihydrofuran pairing at the end, the toxicity was reduced by about 4.5 times; Toxicity also decreases when double lactone is present.

4. Actual situation of Aflatoxin contamination in Vietnam

AF pollution at a low level of 0-5ppb (accounting for 67.91%) is mainly, the rate exceeding the permitted standard of the Ministry of Health is 23.04% (56/243 samples).

- Dau Ngoc Hao and colleagues studied the level of mold and Aflatoxin contamination in maize in Son La and Thanh Hoa provinces. The analysis of 24 samples of maize and 24 samples of maize showed that these samples were infected with *A.flavus* at high frequency, from 50-80%.

- To assess the presence of Aflatoxin B1 in reality, the Institute of Public Health Hygiene in Ho Chi Minh City has conducted a review of food samples circulating in the market or brought by processing companies and facilities. to test registration. Results showed that in 115 samples (including products made from peanuts such as fish skin peanuts, peanut candy etc ...; soy sauce made from soybeans; vegetarian canned foods made from beans and flour; coffee ; fodder) Aflatoxin B1 is present in 30% of coffee samples; 42.9% soy sauce samples; 66.7% of vegetarian canned samples; 68.2% of peanuts and peanut products. In particular, Aflatoxin B1 has a high rate in 94.6% of animal feed samples. Thus, on average, there are 3 samples for all types of Aflatoxin B1 toxin. If based on the permitted standard, only soy sauce samples, although up to 42.9% have Aflatoxin B1, but only at 1.87 - 5.90 ppb (the permitted standard is 10ppb), but in samples most have Aflatoxin B1 with very high content. Especially, there are samples containing from 140 - 300 ppb.

Some practical examples in Vietnam are as follows:

Fish eating food contaminated with Aflatoxin will also be damaged, digestive disorders of the liver and pancreas, leading to serious consequences, if mild, grow slowly, stunted, worse, swollen liver, liver necrosis. Different fish species have different susceptibility to Aflatoxin. Pangasius of Vietnam and US catfish were classified as fairly tolerant of Aflatoxin but still severely affected. Experiments of the Department of Fisheries of Can Tho University showed that with the AFB1 dose below 2.15 mg / kg, the fish food still grew normally, but when the infection content increased to 10 mg / kg and fed for 45 days The weight gain continued to decrease by 20%.

Experiments on farming passages by the Department of Fisheries, Ho Chi Minh City University of Agriculture and Forestry. HCM also showed similar results: after 10 weeks, at the bottom of the feed for AFB1-free food, the fish gained weight from 16.5 g / fish to 50.3 g / fish; meanwhile, in the field, the feed

contaminated with AFB1 with the concentration of 0.12 mg / kg fish only gained weight from 16.5 g / fish to 43.9 g / fish and the contaminated food was 0.3 mg / kg then the fish only grow to 39 g / fish. If the culture period is extended to 22 weeks, the weight of the fish will be worse, especially when at the end of the experiment, the liver of the fish will be swollen, black and enter the stage of necrosis.

In chickens and ducks, people often see anorexia accompanied by slow growth and tend to shed fluff, feathers. There is hemorrhage under the body. Contrary to the mammalian species, the duck's liver is not fibrous, mainly the degeneration of hepatic parenchyma cells, accompanied by rapid regeneration by proliferation of the epithelium of the bile ducts, starting from the perioperative region. Portal vein. After 3 weeks of eating food containing 10% toxins, only small clusters of normal parenchymal cells are surrounded by dense clusters of epithelial cells of the bile duct and then fibrous tissue. Blood stained body, there are many types of hemorrhage and glomerulonephritis in turkeys, but not seen in ducklings. In addition to damage to the liver and kidneys, there is also damage in the duodenum in the form of enteritis. watery immature.

In ducklings, just once for Aflatoxin has caused rapid liver proliferation and reached a maximum after 3 days. In addition, there is peripheral parenchymal degeneration. This damage will subside quickly, so after 10 days some basal cellophiles are found to regenerate parenchymal cells. Similar injuries can also occur when a single dose of DMN or cytazin is given.

In ducklings, after 30 days of feeding with Aflatoxin, the liver is larger than normal and brown or slightly green; Damaged liver surface, sometimes forming obvious small nodules. Right from the first weekend of the diet, parenchymal cells swell, the cytoplasm has acidophilic particles; some cells are about to die; hypertonic and hyperpigmentation; bile duct proliferation is now evident and "oval cells" appear; Ray pattern arrangement from the area around the portal vein. After two weeks, the cytoplasm with more vacuoles appeared more pronounced and the bile duct proliferation was great. After 3 weeks, small nodules in the liver containing proliferating cells were separated from the bile ducts with epithelial saliva. Renal disorders are evident after three weeks: the kidneys swell to light brown color, in dilated tubes, inside there are many protein fragments in an abnormal amount. In some degenerating epithelial cells it is evident that large nuclei have a peculiar shape.

One can comment that the phenomenon of enlarged liver cells (giant cells and enlargement (giant nuclei) seen in cattle, ducklings, turkeys, and in broiler chickens only enlarge. No enlarged liver cells.

A minimum dose of 0.8 mg / kg of Aflatoxin in chickens should be minimum to cause the first changes in the liver.

In humans, a series of studies have shown an increased incidence of primary liver cancer in areas with high rates of exposure to Aflatoxin, but how the mechanism of action of Aflatoxin remains controversial. However, the association of Aflatoxin B1 with DNA of DNA cells in patients with primary liver cancer was found in peripheral blood, placenta blood and umbilical cord blood. pregnant women exposed to Aflatoxin B1. There is also an association between Aflatoxin B1 exposure and gene mutations in these patients, most notably the mutation of the p53 gene - a programmed gene that controls cell death; When this gene mutation will increase cell life, the risk of the cell becoming malignant.

For pregnant women, absorbing certain amounts will lead to birth defects or birth defects, which can cause stillbirth.

Many studies in residential areas in different countries around the world have shown that the actual Aflatoxin concentration in food is related to the risk of liver cancer in those regions.

5. Conclusion

The prevention of Aflatoxin poisoning is very important. Therefore, we propose some solutions as follows:

Practicing good agricultural production (GAP) at every stage from seed selection (to withstand pests and high drought); soil preparation; fertilizing enough fertilizer, enough water when about to harvest; Proper and proper use of plant protection chemicals; harvest at the right time (when dry).

Post-harvest products must be treated, graded and dried immediately to achieve a moisture content lower than 9% for peanuts and less than 13-14% for corn. Remove bad, discolored seeds and pack 2-3 sealed bags for storage with labels and packaging according to hygiene and safety quality standards set by the Ministry of Health. In order to proactively drying corn and groundnut after harvest, it is necessary to improve the equipment for separating corn kernels, specifically: On the corn seed-trailer, the thermal relay and blower should be added to dry the maize products. water standard part as prescribed.

People also should not eat peanuts mold, when peeled peanuts that inside is yellow, dark blue, which is infected with Aflatoxin; Do not buy groundnut products without labels; have labels but do not indicate the expiry date or the expiry date; do not specify the place of production ...

In addition, the use of food contaminated with mold should not be used as food for cattle. Because when animals eat moldy food, toxins will stay in the body and when we eat them, we will also get mold toxins. Therefore, we must have a way to prevent livestock as well as food for cattle. Precautions are as follows:

- Should choose new raw materials as animal feed.
- Regularly check raw materials before, during storage and use to mix food for pets.
- Check and control humidity and suitable temperature during the process of storing materials.
- Preserving ingredients in a dry place.
- Control and eradicate insects, insects, mice in stock: respiratory insects, burning nutrients to produce H₂O, moistening materials to help mold grow at the same time when moving them, they have brought mushroom spores Quick release in stock.
- Using anti-mold chemicals: there are many different chemicals that can prevent mold infection in food: propionic, lactic, sorbic, benzoic and acetic. In particular, relatively safe, non-toxic and highly effective substance to prevent mold growth in feed is propionic acid and its salts. Depending on the fungus and source of infection, use chemicals appropriately. For example, *Aspergillus flavus* fungi infected with maize kernels can be controlled by 2% ammonia or 1% propionic acid.
- Deactivating mycotoxins by physical and chemical methods: in addition to measures such as heat treatment, lighting, use of ozone to oxidize mycotoxins and use of NH₃ alkali, the use of surface adsorbents types of mycotoxins appear to be the most effective and least costly today.

Surveying the qualifications and knowledge of agricultural producers about the toxic effects of contaminated agricultural products on human health.

According to estimates by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), about 25% of the world's agricultural products are seriously affected by mycotoxins, mostly still aflatoxins.

Aflatoxin is the main toxin produced by the mold *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus paraticus*. Including Aflatoxin family, toxins Aflatoxin B₁, B₂, G₁, G₂ are common. Aflatoxin B₁ appears primarily and is the most toxic substance.

Aflatoxins have a very stable chemical structure and are not destroyed by heat, light, acid, alkali, or prolong storage time, so when aflatoxin has appeared, it is difficult to remove them from raw materials or food. breed.

Aflatoxins are potentially carcinogenic. When this toxin enters the body has the ability to reduce resistance, can cause acute and chronic toxicity in animals and humans. The most serious and most dangerous is the possibility of causing cirrhosis and liver cancer.

The damage caused by aflatoxin to public health as well as the economy is not small. Therefore, the problem of preserving food, agricultural products, using safe food as well as not using the food that has been broken down, suspected of being contaminated by mold is a very urgent matter which is very important in terming Current liver cancer treatment. Today, the future research direction of scientists is to find ways to prevent aflatoxin contamination by biological methods (biological struggle techniques).

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